
PROCEDURE FOR STATE REGISTRY OF RIGHTS TO BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS

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Abstract.

State registration procedure of buildings and structures, information, registration procedure based on legal documents after the completion of a building or structure on land plots allocated according to the established procedure, according to state registration in order to register and create a database.

Keywords.

Right to registration, register, database, above-ground - underground buildings, operational management.

Property rights to buildings and structures located on the ground, above the ground and underground, the right to manage the economy and the right to operational management. should be carried out.

The right of a certain legal entity or individual to buildings and structures located on a separate plot of land and having a separate cadastral number, including auxiliary buildings next to them, is an object of registration. Rights to various auxiliary buildings are not registered separately from the main building or structure.

State registration of ownership rights to apartments and non-residential premises in multi-apartment buildings is carried out separately for each owner. The rights to housing belonging to housing construction companies are registered in the name of the relevant company, with the list of members of this company attached.

The rights to buildings and structures whose construction is completed and accepted for use in the prescribed manner are transferred from the state register. In the event that buildings and structures owned by legal entities and individuals are included in the charter fund of newly created legal entities, the property rights to these buildings and structures are registered in the name of newly created legal entities.

Original copies of documents must be submitted for state registration of rights to real estate.

The documents confirming the establishment of property rights to buildings and structures are as follows:

- the decision of the mayor of the city (district) to approve the act of the commission on accepting the completed building, structure, house into use;
- purchase, gift, exchange, inheritance, lease, contracts and transfer-acceptance of enterprises, privatized deeds of state property, as well as decisions issued by the court, approved and presented by notary offices;

State registration of the right to buildings and structures is carried out if there are relevant documents confirming this right.

By the registering organization during the state registration of the right to buildings and structures::

- carries out on-site inspection of the application and legal documents attached to it, their legality, concluded agreements, the condition of buildings and structures, examines the cadastral volume, and determines the number of participants in the joint ownership right, if relevant documents are available , examines their shares and compares with the state register whether there is an application, the rights to real estate and the agreements concluded on it, from other persons, during the state registration of these buildings and structures. .Bir nechta yuridik va jismoniy shaxslarga umumiy ulushli mulk huquq-ida tegishli bo'lgan binolar va inshootlarga bo'lgan huquqlar, mulkdorlar nomiga huquq belgilovchi hujjatlarda ko'rsatilgan ulushlarda ro'yxatdan o'tkaziladi.

If the participants of shared property rights have determined by mutual agreement the procedure for using individual parts of the common building and structure (rooms, apartments, etc.) in accordance with their shares, and this agreement is notarized, then such an agreement it must be registered at their request. In cases where the documents determining the right are presented by the family members or heirs of the owners who have been declared missing or dead by the court, for buildings and structures rights,

according to the submitted documents on property rights to them, they will be registered in the order of inheritance.

State registration of property rights to buildings and structures and other material rights, rights to real estate and agreements concluded on it, the relevant rights of certain legal and physical persons to these objects in the state register, restriction, cancellation of rights, rights to real estate and agreements concluded about it, and by creating a computer database and reporting on the state of state cadastre objects of buildings and structures and their use, submits to the unified system of state cadastres in the prescribed manner.

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